

D2.9. Report on strategic links established and strategic developments

WP2 Integrative Strategic Research Agenda

Responsible Partner: VISAVET-UCM

Contributing partners: RIVM

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	Report on strategic links established and strategic developments
WP and task	WP2, Task 2.2. Strategic interactions with EU projects and initiatives
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Due month of the deliverable	M49
Actual submission month	M49
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: <u>Other recipient(s):</u>

Introduction

The three main objectives for WP2 “Integrative Strategic Research Agenda” are the i) identification of priority topics in the domains of foodborne zoonoses (FBZ), antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and emerging threats (ET); ii) development of the strategic research agenda (SRA); and 3) encouragement of strategic interactions with related EU projects and initiatives. In order to meet the third objective and fulfil Task 2.2 “Strategic interactions with EU projects and initiatives”, two previous deliverables were produced (D2.3. Report on the identification of relevant EU projects and initiatives and the procedure to identify potential strategic interactions & D2.4. Report on potential strategic interactions with EU projects and initiatives). These deliverables included a detailed description regarding the objectives, impact and strategic interactions derived from the interaction between OHEJP Joint Research (JRP) and Integrative (JIP) projects and other European projects.

In this Deliverable 2.9., we present a summary of the information compiled by WP2 in order to address the third objective. The activities can be summarized as follows:

1. Identification of relevant EU-projects and initiatives.
2. Strategic interactions between OHEJP projects and other EU projects and initiatives.

1. Identification of relevant EU-projects and initiatives.

The main objective was to perform a review of relevant EU research projects and related initiatives that overlap in scope with OHEJP projects in order to produce an online inventory to facilitate the identification of potential strategic interactions within the OHEJP consortium. For this reason, information collected from the CORDIS database, as well as OHEJP partners, was compiled in a repository that has been updated three times a year since the beginning of the OHEJP. In this inventory different information was included to allow an easy and quick overview of projects related to the OHEJP. The information included in the repository can be summarized as follows:

- Table with basic information regarding the projects/initiatives (acronym of the project, full name, contact person and e-mail, coordinator’s institution and website).
- Information Sheet for each project/initiative, including name of the project/initiative, acronym, logo, website, contact person (e-mail), coordinator’s institution, website, funding programme, duration, total budget, consortium, objectives and work programmes.
- Gantt chart or at least actual start and end date to show each project duration.
- OHEJP partners (institution and project contact person) (if any) involved in the identified projects/initiatives.
- OHEJP matrix figure to visualise the scientific scope of the relevant projects/initiatives.

Figure 1 presents an overview of the **EU projects and initiatives repository** (spreadsheet) that has been updated regularly to create opportunities for collaboration. The repository is available to all OHEJP consortium through the OHEJP website (Intranet_Home_Groups_OHEJP Consortium Members_Documents) and in this way all the OHEJP members, especially OHEJP JRP (Joint Research Projects), JIP (Joint Integrative Projects) and PhD project leaders, have this information summarized in a manageable and easy-to-use tool with the most relevant information.

Figure 1. EU projects and initiatives repository (version 8) available on the OHEJP intranet.

a) Gantt chart:

Acronym	Funding	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
EQAS	In-kind							
ESFRI	EU H2020							
GMI	In-kind							
JPIAMR	JPI-AMR projects							
ELIXIR	H2020+public sources							
CwG-SCAR	Some actions CASA							
STAR-IDAZ IRC	In-kind							
SIRCAH	EU H2020							
LEAP-AGRI	EU H2020							
VetBioNet	EU H2020							
TRANSVAC2	EU H2020							
EUROBIOTOX	EU H2020							
PIGSs	EU H2020							
eNOTICE	EU H2020							
RAKIP	ANSES, DTU, BFR							
IMPACT	EFSA							
HealthyLivestock	EU H2020							
SOUND control	EU H2020							
SIMBA	EU H2020							
PhagoPROD	EU H2020							
EHDEN	EU H2020							
HIDALGO	EU H2020							
PERITAS	EULAC-Health							
DISARM	EU H2020							
SHARP JA	EU Health Programme							
SAFECONSUME	EU H2020							
ROADMAP	EU H2020							
EOSC-Pillar	EU H2020							
GNA NDw	EU H2020							
ICRAD	EU H2020							
Eur. Burden Dis. Network	COST Action							
ENDVAT	EU H2020							
AVANT	EU H2020							
VEO	EU H2020							
MOOD	EU H2020							
GloPID-R SEC 2	EU H2020							
PANGAIA	EU H2020							
EVA-GLOBAL	EU H2020							
ELIXIR-CONVERGE	EU H2020							
IS_MIRRI21	EU H2020							
ZODIAC	IAEA							
SPRINGBOARD	EU H2020							

b) OHEJP partners* involved in the EU projects and initiatives:

Acronym	BE		DE		DK		ES		FI		FR		FR		FR		HU		LV		IT		NL		NO		PL		PT		RO		SE		UK				
	SIN	RKI	BFR	FU	DTU	SSI	ISCH	INIA	UCM	THL	FI	RUK	IP	FR	AR	SE	INRA	MEH	H	BIOR	ISS	IZSA	IZSLE	R	RIVM	WUR	FHI	NVI	PVE	T	INSA	INIAV	ISPV	FoHM	SYA	PHE	APHA		
EQAS																																							
CWG-SCAR																																							
STAR-IDAZ IRC																																							
LEAP-AGRI																																							
VetBioNet																																							
TRANSVAC2																																							
EUROBIOTOX																																							
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RAKIP																																							
IMPACT																																							
HealthyLivestock																																							
SOUND control																																							
SIMBA																																							
PERITAS																																							
DISARM																																							
SHARP JA																																							
SAFECONSUME																																							
ROADMAP																																							
EOSC-Pillar																																							
ICRAD																																							
Eur. Burden Dis. Network																																							
AVANT																																							
VEO																																							
MOOD																																							
PANGAIA																																							
EVA-GLOBAL																																							
ELIXIR-CONVERGE																																							
IS_MIRRI21																																							

* Med institutions in yellow; Vet institutions in blue; Med/Vet institutions in green.

Since 2018, a total of 60 EU projects and initiatives have been included in the repository (Table 1). In table 1, the **information sheet** of each project and initiative, produced by WP2, is also available by clicking the acronym.

Table 1. List and information sheets of EU projects and initiatives included in the repository since 2018 (alphabetical order).

N	Acronym*	Project/Initiative
1	<u>AVANT</u>	Alternatives to Veterinary ANTimicrobials
2	<u>COMPARE</u>	Collaborative Management Platform for detection and Analyses of (Re-) emerging and foodborne outbreaks in Europe
3	<u>CORBEL</u>	Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science Services
4	<u>CWG-SCAR</u>	Collaborative Working Group on European Animal Health & Welfare Research (CWG), EU Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR)
5	<u>DISARM</u>	Disseminating Innovative Solutions for Antibiotic Resistance Management
6	<u>EFFORT</u>	Ecology from Farm to Fork of microbial drug Resistance and Transmission
7	<u>EHDEN</u>	European Health Data and Evidence Network
8	<u>ELIXIR</u>	Distributed infrastructure for biological data
9	<u>ELIXIR-CONVERGE</u>	Connect and align ELIXIR Nodes to deliver sustainable FAIR life-science data management services
10	<u>EMERGE</u>	Efficient response to highly dangerous and emerging pathogens at EU level
11	<u>ENGAGE</u>	Establishing Next Generation sequencing Ability for Genomic analysis in Europe
12	<u>eNOTICE</u>	European Network Of CBRN Training Centers
13	<u>ENOVAT</u>	European Network for Optimization of Veterinary Antimicrobial Treatment
14	<u>EOSC-hub</u>	European Open Science Cloud-EOSC-hub
15	<u>EOSC-Pillar</u>	Coordination and Harmonisation of National Initiatives, Infrastructures and Data services in Central and Western Europe
16	<u>EQAS</u>	External Quality Control System (EQAS)
17	<u>ESFRI</u>	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
18	<u>EU CBRN CoE</u>	European Union Chemical Biological Radiological and Nuclear Risk Mitigation Centres of Excellence Initiative
19	<u>EUROBIOTOX</u>	European programme for the establishment of validated procedures for the detection and identification of biological toxins
20	<u>European Burden of Disease Network</u>	European Burden of Disease Network
21	<u>EVAg</u>	European Virus Archive goes Global
22	<u>EVA-GLOBAL</u>	European Virus Archive GLOBAL
23	<u>FLEXPOL</u>	Antimicrobial FLEXible POLymers for its use in hospital environments
24	<u>GloPID-R SEC 2</u>	GloPID-R Secretariat
25	<u>GMI</u>	Global Microbial Identifier
26	<u>GNA NOW</u>	Novel Gram-Negative Antibiotic now
27	<u>HealthyLivestock</u>	Tackling Antimicrobial Resistance through improved livestock Health and Welfare
28	<u>HIDALGO</u>	HPC and Big Data Technologies for Global Systems
29	<u>ICRAD</u>	International Coordination of Research on Infectious Animal Diseases
30	<u>IMPACT</u>	Standardising molecular detection methods to IMprove risk assessment capacity for foodborne protozoan Parasites, using Cryptosporidium in ready-to-eat salad as a model organism

N	Acronym*	Project/Initiative
31	INFACT	Joint Action on Health Information
32	INNUENDO	A novel cross-sectorial platform for the integration of genomics in surveillance of foodborne pathogens
33	IoF2020	Internet of Food and Farm 2020
34	IS MIRRI21	Implementation and Sustainability of Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure for 21st Century
35	JAMRAI	European Joint Action on antimicrobial resistance and associated interactions
36	JPIAMR	Joint Programming Initiative on Antimicrobial Resistance
37	LEAP-AGRI	A long term EU-Africa research and innovation partnership on food and nutrition security and sustainable agriculture
38	MOOD	MONitoring Outbreak events for Disease surveillance in a data science context
39	NEOH	Network for Evaluation of One Health
40	PANGAIA	Pan-genome Graph Algorithms and Data Integration
41	PERITAS	Molecular ePIdemiological studiEs on pathways of tRansmission and long lasTing cApacity building to prevent cyStic echinococcosis infection
42	PhagoPROD	GMP manufacturing & GLP diagnostic: Towards a personalised phage therapy against antimicrobial resistance
43	PIGSs	Program for Innovative Global Prevention of <i>Streptococcus suis</i>
44	PREPARE	Platform foR European Preparedness Against (Re-)emerging Epidemics
45	RAKIP	Risk assessment modelling & knowledge integration platform
46	ROADMAP	Rethinking of Antimicrobial Decision-systems in the Management of Animal Production
47	SAFECONSUME	SafeConsumE: Safer food through changed consumer behavior: Effective tools and products, communication strategies, education and a food safety policy reducing health burden from foodborne illnesses
48	SAPHIR	Strengthening Animal Production and Health through the Immune Response
49	SHARP JA	Joint Action on Strengthened International Health Regulations and Preparedness in the EU
50	SIMBA	Sustainable innovation of microbiome applications in food system
51	SIRCAH	Secretariat for the International Research Consortium on Animal Health
52	SOUND control	Standardizing OUtput-basedsurveillance to controlNon-regulated Diseases of cattle in the EU
53	SPRINGBOARD	Springboard for excellence in advanced development of antibacterials
54	STAR-IDAZ IRC	STAR-IDAZ International Research Consortium on Animal Health (IRC)
55	SWINOSTICS	Swine diseases field diagnostics toolbox
56	TRANSVAC2	European Vaccine Research and Development Infrastructure
57	VEO	Versatile Emerging Infectious Disease Observatory
58	VetBioNet	Veterinary Biocontained facility Network for excellence in animal infectious disease research and experimentation
59	VIVALDI	Veterinary Validadtion of Point-of-Care Detection Instrument
60	ZODIAC	Zoonotic Disease Integrated Action

*Information sheet of the project is available by clicking the acronym of the project and initiative.

The scientific scope of the identified EU projects/initiatives is also visualized in relation to the **OHEJP matrix** consisting of three domains (FBZ, AMR, ET), five themes (Analytical methods, Host-microbe interaction, Epidemiology, Risk assessment and socio-economic impact and Intervention) (Table 2). This table also shows which EU projects/initiatives provides platforms, repositories and/or guidelines with

respect to one of the three domains (table 2). This classification helps the OHEJP project leaders to identify the EU projects/initiatives that could be of interest to establish interactions promoting scientific collaborations.

Table 2. OHEJP matrix including the relevant EU projects/initiatives.

Domains Themes	Foodborne zoonoses	Antimicrobial resistance	Emerging threats
Analytical methods	COMPARE, ELIXIR, ENGAGE, EQAS, EUROBIOTOX, European Burden of Disease Network, GMI, ICRAD, IMPACT, INNUENDO, IoF2020, PANGAIA, PIGs, SAPHIR, SWINOSTICS, VEO, VIVALDI, ZODIAC	AVANT, EFFORT, ELIXIR, ENOVAT, EQAS, European Burden of Disease Network, FLEXPOL, GNA-NOW, HealthyLivestock, ICRAD, JPIAMR, PANGAIA, SPRINGBOARD, VEO	COMPARE, ELIXIR, EMERGE, EUROBIOTOX, European Burden of Disease Network, GMI, ICRAD, PANGAIA, SAPHIR, VetBioNet, ZODIAC
Host-microbe interaction	ENGAGE, ICRAD, SAPHIR	AVANT, EFFORT, ENGAGE, FLEXPOL, ICRAD, JPIAMR, SPRINGBOARD	ICRAD, PERITAS, PhagoPROD, SAPHIR, SIMBA, VetBioNet
Epidemiology	COMPARE, ICRAD, INNUENDO, PIGs, SAFECONSUME, SOUND control, VEO, MOOD	AVANT, EFFORT, ICRAD, JPIAMR, MOOD, ROADMAP, SOUND control, VEO	COMPARE, ICRAD, MOOD, PERITAS, PREPARE, SOUND control
Risk assessment and socio-economic impact	COMPARE, European Burden of Disease Network, ICRAD, IoF2020, MOOD, SAFECONSUME, SOUND control, VEO	AVANT, EFFORT, European Burden of Disease Network, ICRAD, JAMRAI, JPIAMR, MOOD, ROADMAP, SOUND control, VEO	COMPARE, European Burden of Disease Network, ICRAD, MOOD, PERITAS, PREPARE, SOUND control, VetBioNet
Intervention	EHDEN, European Burden of Disease Network, ICRAD, IoF2020, MOOD, SAFECONSUME, SAPHIR, SHARP JA, SOUND control	AVANT, DISARM, EFFORT, EHDEN, ENOVAT, ESFRI, European Burden of Disease Network, FLEXPOL, GNA-NOW, HealthyLivestock, ICRAD, JAMRAI, JPIAMR, MOOD, ROADMAP, SHARP JA, SOUND control	COMPARE, EHDEN, European Burden of Disease Network, GloPID-R SEC 2, ICRAD, MOOD, PERITAS, PhagoPROD, PREPARE, SAPHIR, SHARP JA, SIMBA, SOUND control, VetBioNet
Platform Repository Guidelines	CORBEL, CWG-SCAR, EHDEN, ELIXIR, ELIXIR-CONVERGE, EOSC, EOSC-Pillar, EQAS, ESFRI, European Burden of Disease Network, HIDALGO, INFAC, INNUENDO, IoF2020, IS_MIRRI21, LEAP-AGRI, MOOD, NEOH, PANGAIA, RAKIP, SAFECONSUME, SIRCAH, SOUND control, STAR-IDAZ IRC, TRANSVAC2, VEO, ZODIAC	EHDEN, ELIXIR, ELIXIR-CONVERGE, ENOVAT, EOSC, EOSC-Pillar, EQAS, ESFRI, European Burden of Disease Network, HIDALGO, IS_MIRRI21, JAMRAI, JPIAMR, MOOD, PANGAIA, SOUND control, TRANSVAC2, VEO	CORBEL, CWG-SCAR, EHDEN, ELIXIR, ELIXIR-CONVERGE, EMERGE, enotice, EOSC, EOSC-Pillar, ESFRI, EU CBRN CoE, European Burden of Disease Network, EVAg, EVA-GLOBAL, GloPID-R SEC 2, HIDALGO, INFAC, IS_MIRRI21, MOOD, NEOH, PANGAIA, PREPARE, SIRCAH, SOUND control, STAR-IDAZ IRC, TRANSVAC2, VetBioNet, ZODIAC

Moreover, although CORDIS has been the main database used to gather all these EU projects and initiatives, eight **JPIAMR calls** were also included in another spreadsheet together with their information sheets. Table 3 provides a summary of the projects included in each JPIAMR call.

Table 3. JPIAMR calls and projects included in the OHEJP repository of EU projects and initiatives.

THIRD JPIAMR JOINT CALL "TRANSMISSIONS DYNAMICS": BEAT-AMR , COLLATERAL , DAMAGE , EMerGE-NeT , PNEUMO-SPREAD , Restrict-Pneumo-AMR , TransPred , HECTOR , JumpAR , MACOTRA , PET-Risk , PREPARE , SpARK , ST-131 transmission , STARCS , TransComp-ESC-R , AWARE-WWTP , DARWIN , Gene-gas , MODERN
FOURTH JPIAMR JOINT CALL "AMR NETWORKS/WORKING GROUPS": Behavioural , VetCAST , Flies , Consensus , CAM strategy , AMRIC Network , BEAM Alliance , AMR-RDT , Bridging gap , AACTING , Histidine Kinase , Phage Forward , Nitrofurantoin
FIFTH JPIAMR JOINT CALL "COMPARISON OF PREVENTION, CONTROL AND INTERVENTION STRATEGIES FOR AMR INFECTIONS THROUGH MULTIDISCIPLINARY STUDIES, INCLUDING ONE HEALTH APPROACHES": AB-assistant , ARMIS , ASB , ExcludeMRSA , ImpresU , INART , REDUCEAMU , OPEN Stewardship , PILGRIM , Resilience
SIXTH JPIAMR JOINT CALL "INNOVATION AGAINST ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANT BACTERIA: NEW TARGETS, COMPOUNDS AND TOOLS": ANTIBIO-LAB , Anti-Persistence , CRISPRAttack , DISRUPT , Explore , FLAV4AMR , MTI4MDR-TB , RESET-ME , RIBOTARGET , SCAN
SEVENTH JPIAMR CALL "WORKING TO IMPROVE SURVEILLANCE": NETESE , ARCH , SOLIDNESS , KlebNet , NeWIS , PRAISE , CoEval-AMR , WAWES , Towards Developing , ICALM
EIGHT JPIAMR CALL "WORKING TOGETHER TO BUILD THE JPIAMR VIRTUAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE": GAP-ONE , AMRIC , AMR Dx Global , CONNECT , IRAADD , NEAR-AMR , VeRI BEAM , TT
NINTH JPIAMR CALL "DIAGNOSTICS AND SURVEILLANCE": AntiRYB , EMBARK , IDAREMS , IDx , K-STaR , MAD-tech-AMR , MAGiCIAN , MAGITICS , OASIS , SAMPAN , TARGET , TRIuMPH
TENTH JPIAMR CALL "JPIAMR Network Plus 2020": CoEval-AMR PHASE 2 , SHARENET , Seq4AMR , GAP-ONE-2 , GIFTS-AMR , PAAN , AEPIC

* Information of the project is available by clicking the acronym.

Moreover, the **JIP COVRIN** (One Health research integration on SARS-CoV-2 emergence, risk assessment and preparedness) performed a scoping review of European Union (EU)-supported SARS-CoV-2 research activities that overlap with COVRIN to avoid redundancy and ensure optimal use of resources (COVRIN deliverable D3.1. Scoping review of European Union-supported COVID-19 research activities). A total of 63 SARS-CoV-2 initiatives (consortia), 28 other relevant initiatives, 9 COVID-19 data- and laboratory-related efforts, and 17 Research Infrastructures (including 2 SARSCoV-2 initiative duplicate entries) were included in the database that has been published in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5533808>).

During the lifetime of the OHEJP, **WP2** has contacted several projects and initiatives (ELIXIR, ENOVAT, European Burden of Disease Network, GloPID-R SEC 2, HealthyLivestock, HIDALGO, IS_MIRRI21, JPI-AMR, PANGAIA, PhagoPROD, SPRINGBOARD and VetBioNet) in order to establish a fruitful collaboration or to identify possible synergies between them and the OHEJP projects. For this, WP2 elaborated the list of candidate projects taking into account the EU project repository, selecting only projects that had not been contacted before by other OHEJP members. Besides, the duration of the project, as well as the scope, covering the majority of OHEJP project topics, were also taken into account for the selection of EU projects/initiatives. Moreover, WP2 has participated in several dissemination activities [e.g. CONNECT Network final meeting, questionnaires from "Open call for data on use of antimicrobials in animals" distributed by European Medicines Agency and Global Antimicrobial Resistance Platform for One Burden Estimates (GAP-ONE) and One Health Latinoamerica (OHLA)] to increase the OHEJP visibility and foster strategic interactions with related EU projects and initiatives.

2. Strategic interactions between OHEJP projects and other EU projects and initiatives.

Several actions have been taken to facilitate the interactions between the OHEJP JIP, JRP and PhD projects with relevant and related EU projects and initiatives. These activities include the repository of EU projects/initiatives, direct contact with project leaders, attendance to congresses/meetings, cogwheel workshops, etc. As a result of this active search for related EU projects and initiatives to avoid duplicity and strengthen collaboration between projects that are working with the same pathogens, technologies, platforms, etc., several interactions have been initiated during the lifetime of the OHEJP project. Table 4 provides a summary of all the interactions that have been reported to the OHEJP coordination team, which have been reported through several One Health EJP deliberables:

- D1.14. Summary Progress Report Year 4
- D3.7. First periodic report on ongoing JRPs
- D3.11. Second periodic report on ongoing JRPs
- D3.15. Third periodic report on JRP
- D3.17. Final reports of 1st call JRPs and evaluation reports
- D4.3. 1st cogwheel workshop report with COMPARE
- D4.6. Report from 2nd cogwheel workshop (EFFORT)
- D4.10. First periodic report on ongoing JIPs
- D4.11. Report from 3rd cogwheel workshop (INNUENDO, IRIDA, COMPARE)
- D4.14. Report from 4th cogwheel workshop (INFACIT)
- D4.18. Report from 5th cogwheel workshop (JPI-AMR: MAGITICS, K-STaR, OASIS, TRIuMPH, IDx)
- D4.20. Report from 6th cogwheel workshop (SafeConsume)
- D4.22. Third periodic report on JIPs
- D4.23. Report from 7th cogwheel workshop (VEO, MOOD)
- D4.25. Report from 8th cogwheel workshop (ELIXIR)
- D6.21. Third periodic report on PhD projects

Table 4. Summary of the interactions between EU projects/initiatives and OHEJP JRP, JIP and PhD projects.

N	Acronym EU project/initiative	Acronym OHEJP project	Source*
1	AACTING (JPIAMR)	ARDIG	D1.14., D.3.11.
2	AVANT	ARDIG, METAPRO, MoMIR-PPC	D.3.11., D3.15.
3	COMPARE	FED-AMR, LISTADAPT, METASTAVA, NOVA, RaDAR, PARADISE, 1 st and 3 rd cogwheel workshop	D1.14., D.3.7., D.3.11., D3.15., D4.3., D4.11.
4	NEOH (COST Action)	ORION	D4.10.
5	ASF-STOP (COST Action)	NOVA	D.3.11., D3.15.
6	Euro-FBP (COST Action)	TOXOSOURCES	D3.15.
7	DISARM	WP1	PMT
8	EAT2beNICE	TOXOSOURCES	D3.15.
9	EFFORT	FED-AMR, ARDIG, FULLFORCE, LISTADAPT, METAPRO, METASTAVA, RaDAR, 2 nd cogwheel workshop	D1.14., D.3.7., D.3.11., D3.15, D4.6., D6.21.
10	ELIXIR	8th cogwheel workshop	D4.25.
11	ENGAGE	FULLFORCE	D3.15.
12	ENOVAT	IMPART	D.3.11., D3.17.
13	ERA-NET ANIHWA consortium	MoMIR-PPC	D.3.7.
14	ERASMUS IDOH	WP1, WP6	PMT

Table 4. Summary of the interactions between EU projects/initiatives and OHEJP JRP, JIP and PhD projects.

N	Acronym EU project/initiative	Acronym OHEJP project	Source*
15	GAP-ONE	METAPRO	D6.21.
16	GenEpiO	ORION, BeONE	D1.14., D4.10.
17	HealthyLivestock	WP2, BIOPIGEE	PMT
18	HECTOR	WORLDCOM	D3.15.
19	IDx	5th cogwheel workshop	D4.18.
20	IMPACT (EFSA)	PARADISE, TOXOSOURCES	D3.15.
21	INFACIT	4th cogwheel workshop	D4.14.
22	INNUENDO	METASTAVA, 3rd cogwheel workshop	D.3.11., D4.11.
23	IRIDA	METASTAVA, 3rd cogwheel workshop	D.3.11., D4.11.
24	JAMRAI	ARDIG, WP2	D1.14., D3.15.
25	KlebNET (JPIAMR)	Codes4Strains, Medvetklebs	D.3.11., D6.21.
26	K-STAR (JPIAMR)	FARMED, 5th cogwheel workshop	D3.15., D4.18.
27	MAGITICS	5th cogwheel workshop	D4.18.
28	MEDILABSECURE	MAD-Vir, TELEVIR	D.3.7., D3.15.
29	MOOD	7th cogwheel workshop	D4.23.
30	NEAR-AMR	METAPRO	D6.21.
31	OASIS	WORLDCOM, 5th cogwheel workshop	D3.15., D4.18.
32	PERITAS	MEME	D3.15.
33	PREZODE	WP1	PMT
34	RAKIP	ORION, RADAR	D.3.11., D4.22.
35	ROAD MAP	WP1	PMT
36	SafeConsume	TOXOSOURCES, 6th cogwheel workshop	D3.15., D4.20.
37	SHARP	WP2	PMT
38	SIGMA	ORION	D4.10.
39	SISOT	ORION	D4.22.
40	SOLIDNESS (JPIAMR)	FULLFORCE	D3.15.
41	SpARK (JPIAMR)	Codes4Strains, Medvetklebs	D.3.11., D6.21.
42	Stance4Health	TOXOSOURCES	D3.15.
43	STAR-IDAZ IRC	WP1	PMT
44	TO-REACH	WP1	PMT
45	TRluMPH	5th cogwheel workshop	D4.18.
46	VACDIVA	NOVA	D3.15.
47	VEO	7th cogwheel workshop	D4.23.
48	VetCAST	IMPART	D.3.11.
49	ZODIAC	WP1, WP5	PMT

*D1.14. Summary Progress Report Year 4, D.3.7. First periodic report on ongoing JRPs, D.3.11. Second periodic report on ongoing JRPs, D3.15. Third periodic report on JRP, D3.17. Final reports of 1st call JRPs and evaluation reports, D4.3. 1st cogwheel workshop report with COMPARE, D4.6. Report from 2nd cogwheel workshop (EFFORT), D4.10. First periodic report on ongoing JIPs, D4.11. Report from 3rd cogwheel workshop (INNUENDO, IRIDA, COMPARE), D4.14. Report from 4th cogwheel workshop (INFACIT), D4.18. Report from 5th cogwheel workshop (JPI-AMR: MAGITICS, K-STAR, OASIS, TRluMPH, IDx), D4.20. Report from 6th cogwheel workshop (SafeConsume), D4.22. Third periodic report on JIPs, D4.23. Report from 7th cogwheel workshop (VEO, MOOD), D4.25. Report from 8th cogwheel workshop (ELIXIR), D6.21. Third periodic report on PhD projects, PMT. Project Management Team.

The information included in table 4 has been translated into a diagram (Figure 2) to show, in a easy and graphical view, the amount of interactions occurred during the life time of the OHEJP project.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of project interactions.

WP2 has been in contact with WP4 to exchange information about some EU projects/initiatives for the selection of possible candidates for the organization of **cogwheel workshops**. This collaboration has been another way of identifying synergies, joint priorities and opportunities for collaboration within the OHEJP or with other EU initiatives. In table 5 there is a list of all the OHEJP projects that attended the different

cogwheel workshops that so far have included a total of 14 EU projects (COMPARE, EFFORT, INNUENDO, IRIDA, INFAC, MAGITICS, K-STaR, OASIS, TRIuMPH, IDx, SafeConsume, VEO, MOOD and ELIXIR).

Table 5. Attendance of OHEJP projects to cogwheel workshops.

Project-domain	OHEJP project	Cogwheel workshop*							
		1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th
JRP-FBZ	ADONIS								
	BeONE								
	BIOPIGEE								
	DISCOVER								
	LISTADAPT								
	MedVetKlebs								
	METASTAVA								
	NOVA								
	TOXOSOURCES								
JRP-AMR	ARDIG								
	FED-AMR								
	FULL-FORCED								
	IMPART								
	RaDAR								
	WORLDCOM								
JRP-ET	IDEMBRU								
	MEEmE								
	PARADISE								
	TELE-Vir								
	TOX-detect								
JIP	CARE								
	COHESIVE								
	MATRIX								
	OH-HARMONY-CAP								
	ORION								
phD-FBZ	EnvDis								
phD-AMR	FARMED								
	VIMOGUT								
phD-ET	PEMbo								
phD-SU	SUSTAIN								

*1st: COMPARE; 2nd: EFFORT; 3rd: INNUENDO & IRIDA; 4th: INFAC; 5th: JPI-AMR (MAGITICS, K-STaR, OASIS, TRIuMPH, IDx); 6th: SafeConsume; 7th: VEO & MOOD; 8th: ELIXIR.

All the interactions between OHEJP projects and other EU projects and initiatives have resulted in **synergetic collaborations** with an important impact in all the projects. The outcomes of these interactions can be summarized as follows:

- a) Share of data, workflows and bioinformatics pipelines
- b) Share of products previously developed (standards, culture media)
- c) Collaboration to develop new methodology and protocols
- d) Expertise in organizing Proficiency Tests
- e) Compatibility of platforms developed
- f) Dissemination of OHEJP results
- g) Share of information on the use of NGS
- h) Submission of project proposals to JPI-AMR and JAMRAI calls
- i) Collaborative publications and workshops

In table 6, some specific collaborations as an example of the active interaction between the OHEJP and other EU projects and initiatives are shown. These examples are a clear reflection of the benefits of these interactions and show their impact on the outcomes from all the EU and OHEJP projects.

Table 6. Examples of specific collaborations between EU and OHEJP projects.

Type of interaction*	Acronym EU project/initiative	Acronym OHEJP projects	Specific collaboration
a)	COMPARE	LISTADAPT, RaDAR, PARADISE	Use of data (ie. genes involved in adaptation and survival) and pipelines (ie. <i>Cryptosporidium</i> pipeline) generated by COMPARE project
a)	EFFORT	LISTADAPT, RaDAR, ARDIG	Use of data (ie. <i>E. coli</i> isolates) generated by EFFORT project
a)	VACDIVA	NOVA	Outputs from NOVA WP4 related to geographical distribution of animals species evaluated the last two years (2019-2020, pig animals and wild boars) have been shared with the VACDIVA project to evaluate the vaccination scenarios for ASF
a)	K-STAR (JPIAMR)	FARMED	Share of analysis workflows for analysing sequencing data
a)	IMPACT (EFSA)	TOXOSOURCES	TOXOSOURCES survey questionnaire and SOP on “Detection of <i>T. gondii</i> in selected fresh produce matrix” were developed based on outcomes of the project IMPACT
a)	COMPARE	NOVA	Bayesian estimates of pig slaughter prevalence (derived from abattoir surveys) were used for the COMPARE source attribution task
a), i)	AACTING (JPIAMR)	ARDIG	Develop common recommendations for improved “One Health” surveillance strategies. These recommendations were presented in a collaborative workshop (ARDIG, AACTING, JPIAMR, European Agencies)
b)	RAKIP	RADAR	The RaDAR model inventory uses the FSK standard that has been developed by the RAKIP initiative
b)	SpARK (JPIAMR)	Medvetklebs	Use the validated SCAI culture method developed by Medvetklebs
b)	AVANT	MoMIR-PPC	Probiotic strains tested in MoMIR-PPC project have been shared with AVANT project
c)	JAMRAI	ARDIG	Collaboration to develop a new method that will allow comparing not harmonized AMR data
c)	MEDILABSECURE	TELEVIR	Both projects will provide an easy portable tool for a rapid identification and response against viral threats
c)	IMPACT (EFSA)	PARADISE	Definition of optimized protocols for the detection and typing of Foodborne Parasites on selected food matrices
d)	SOLIDNESS (JPIAMR)	FULLFORCE	SOLIDNESS expertise in organizing Proficiency Test (PT) within FULLFORCE project
e)	SIGMA	ORION	Assure that the platform developed by ORION is compatible with SIGMA project (facilitate data reuse)
e)	GenEpiO	ORION	Looking for complementarity between both projects (GenEpiO: molecular epidemiology in outbreaks; ORION: surveillance and epidemiological data)
f)	VetCAST ENOVAT	IMPART	Dissemination of OHEJP results to Committees (VetCAST) and COST actions (ENOVAT) kick-off meeting
g)	GenEpiO	BeONE	Ontology for sequencing parameters for BeONE project

Table 6. Examples of specific collaborations between EU and OHEJP projects.

Type of interaction*	Acronym EU project/initiative	Acronym OHEJP projects	Specific collaboration
g)	INNUENDO, IRIDA, COMPARE, EFFORT	METASTAVA	Discussion about the use of NGS for detection or characterization of microorganisms (viruses and bacterias)
h)	KlebNET (JPIAMR)	Medvetklebs	Project submission (KlebNET) to a JPI-AMR call due to previous networking activities within the Medvetklebs project
h), i)	JAMRAI	ARDIG	Discussions on the EARS-Vet project (European harmonised system on AMR in clinical isolates of animals) and a collaborative paper (Mesa-Varona et al. 2021)
i)	SpARK (JPIAMR)	Medvetklebs	Collaborative publication describing two novel species of <i>Klebsiella</i> (<i>K. pasteurii</i> and <i>K. spallanzanii</i>) (Merla et al. 2019)
i)	Euro-FBP (COST Action)	TOXOSOURCES	Collaborative literature review of source attribution for <i>T. gondii</i> infections in Europe

*a) Share of data, pipelines and workflows; b) Share of products previously developed (standards, culture media); c) Collaboration to develop new methodology and protocols; d) Expertise in organizing Proficiency Test; e) Compatibility of platforms developed; f) Dissemination of OHEJP results; g) Discussion about the use of NGS; h) Project submission to JPI-AMR and JAMRAI calls; and i) Collaborative publications and workshops.